

Synthesis of 4-Aminoquinaldines*

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4-Anilinoquinaldines have been prepared by cyclodehydration of β -anilino-crotono-anilides.

The biological oxidation at the 2-position of the quinoline ring¹ led to synthesis of many compounds, in which the 2-position was blocked by suitable substituents, for enhanced antimalarial activity. Sen and Basu² synthesised 2-methylcamoquine which showed promise in limited trials and offered some advantages over the parent drug, camoquine³. The usual preparative methods for the synthesis of 4-aminoquinolines involve condensation of 4-haloquinolines with appropriate aliphatic and aromatic amino compounds. Conversion of the 4-hydroxyquinaldines to the corresponding 4-chloroquinaldines results in considerable amount of tarry products, from which isolation of the desired chloro compound in pure form is somewhat tedious. Further, quinoline ring-closure involving *meta*-substituted anilines often results in 5- and 7-isomers. Thus 4,7-dichloroquinaldine, which was necessary for the above synthesis, was prepared in several steps in an overall yield of 26%.

Possible cyclisation of β -anilino-crotono-anilides to the corresponding 4-anilinoquinaldine offers an attractive alternative synthesis. In the present work, aniline and *m*-chloroaniline were condensed with *p*-acetoacetanilide to afford β -anilino- and β -*m*-chloroanilino-crotono-*p*-methoxyanilide, respectively. On treatment with either polyphosphoric acid or concentrated sulphuric acid, the β -anilino- and β -*m*-chloroanilino-crotono-*p*-methoxyanilide cyclised to afford a mixture of two compounds. Treatment with 1% NaOH solution partially dissolved one fraction which on neutralisation afforded the desired 4-(4'-hydroxyanilino)quinaldine and its 7-chloro analogue, respectively. The alkali-insoluble compound was later identified as 6-methoxy-4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline (*vide infra*). Cyclodehydration with phosphorus pentoxide in xylene or with phosphorus oxychloride in benzene led only to ring closure, affording the corresponding methoxy derivative in a much reduced yield. The sequence of reactions involving *meta*-chloro analogue would also theoretically provide two isomers. The only product, which could be isolated on cyclisation, was the corresponding 7-chloro analogue.

Similar observation was made by Price and Boekelheide⁴ as well as Sen and Basu⁵ in the case of cyclisation of β -anilino- α -ethoxycarbonylacrylamides, which led to ring closure

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1. Mead and Koepfl, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1944, 154, 104.
2. *This Journal*, 1957, 34, 839.
3. Chaudhury, *Bull. Calcutta School of Tropical Medicine*, 1953, p. 32.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 68, 1246.
5. *This Journal*, 1957, 34, 906.

involving *para* position in the case of *meta*-substituted anilines, affording the 7-substituted quinolines only. The methoxy compounds underwent demethylation smoothly on treatment either with concentrated sulphuric acid or with hydrobromic acid (48%) and were identical with the products obtained by direct cyclisation with sulphuric acid or polyphosphoric acid.

The alkali (1%)-insoluble material, obtained by cyclisation with sulphuric acid in this case, was found to be identical with that obtained from the preparation of the anilino analogue; elementary composition determination led to identification of the compounds, confirmed by comparison with the compound obtained by cyclodehydration of *p*-acetoacetaniside⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

β -m-Chloroanilinocrotono-p-methoxyanilide.—A thoroughly stirred mixture of *m*-chloroaniline (0.02*M*, 2.54 g.) and *p*-acetoacetaniside (0.02*M*, 4.12 g.) was kept under vacuum over calcium chloride until the theoretical loss of water was attained. The initial pasty mass gradually hardened to a crystalline solid. Three crystallisations from small volumes of ethanol furnished 5.6 g. (88%) of the compound, m.p. 101–102°. (Found: C, 64.20; H, 5.76; N, 8.50. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires C, 64.45; H, 5.37; N, 8.84%.)

β -Anilinocrotono-p-methoxyanilide was prepared from aniline (0.05*M*, 4.6 g.) and *p*-acetoacetaniside (0.05*M*, 10.3 g.), essentially as described for the *m*-chloroanilino compound. Two crystallisations from small volumes of ethanol provided 9.0 g. of the compound, m.p. 95–96°. (Found: C, 71.90; H, 6.81; N, 9.85. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires C, 72.34; H, 6.39; N, 9.93%.)

6. Campbell *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 11, 803.

4-(4'-Hydroxyanilino)quinaldine

(a). β -Anilinoacrotono-*p*-methoxyanilide (0.015*M*, 4.2 g.) was slowly added to H_2SO_4 (conc., 4.2 ml) so as to maintain the temperature below 5° and kept there for 5 hr. After keeping overnight, the temperature was slowly raised to 100° and kept there for 4 hr. and then left overnight. The cooled mixture was stirred with ice, filtered, and washed with ice water. The material was stirred with a 1% NaOH solution (30 ml) when the product was partially dissolved; it was cooled and filtered. On neutralisation, the compound separated which was collected and washed with cold water. It was crystallised twice from ethanol, m.p. $263-64^\circ$, yield 35%. (Found: C, 77.29; H, 5.98; N, 11.69. $C_{16}H_{14}ON_2$ requires C, 76.80; H, 5.60; N, 11.20%.)

(b). A sample, prepared according to the general procedure of Burekhalter *et al.*⁷ from 4-chloroquinaldine and *p*-aminophenol hydrochloride, recorded no depression on mixed m.p. determination.

(c). 4-(4'-Methoxyanilino)quinaldine (*vide infra*) was treated with H_2SO_4 (conc.) and worked up essentially as described under (a). Mixed m. p. determination with the sample prepared as in (a) recorded no depression. The IR spectra of the compound, prepared by different procedures, were superimposable.

4-(4'-Methoxyanilino)quinaldine

(a). The compound was prepared by condensing 4-chloroquinaldine and *p*-anisidine hydrochloride, essentially as described above for the corresponding hydroxy compound. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. $204-205^\circ$. (Found: C, 77.71; H, 6.41; N, 10.20. $C_{17}H_{16}ON_2$ requires C, 77.27; H, 6.06; N, 10.40%.)

(b). The cyclodehydration of β -anilinoacrotono-*p*-methoxyanilide was carried out with $POCl_3$ in benzene, essentially according to the general method of Price and Boekelheide⁸. After three recrystallisations from aqueous ethanol, the compound melted at $204-205^\circ$, yield 16%.

7-Chloro-4-(4'-hydroxyanilino)quinaldine

(a). β -*m*-Chloroanilinoacrotono-*p*-methoxyanilide (0.007*M*, 2.1 g.) was cyclised with H_2SO_4 (conc.) and worked up to obtain the desired compound, essentially as described above. On two crystallisations from ethanol, the compound melted at $269-270^\circ$, yield 0.51 g. (26%). Mixed m.p. with a sample, prepared according to Sen and Basu⁹, recorded no depression.

The alkali-insoluble material (1.1 g.) was crystallised several times from a large volume of ethanol, m.p. $267-68^\circ$. (Found: C, 68.99; H, 6.35; N, 7.51. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 68.80; H, 5.80; N, 7.40%). Mixed m.p. determination with 6-methoxy-4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline⁹ (*vide infra*) recorded no depression. The IR spectra were also superimposable.

(b). 7-Chloro-4-(4'-methoxyanilino)quinaldine (1g.) (*vide infra*) was demethylated with H_2SO_4 (conc.) as described earlier. On recrystallisation from ethanol, the compound

(0.4 g.) melted at 268-60°. Mixed m.p. with the sample prepared according to Sen and Basu⁴ recorded no depression.

(c). 7-Chloro-4-(4'-methoxyanilino)quinaldino (0.05M, 1.40 g.) and 48% HBr (18 ml) were refluxed for 10 hr. The mixture was cooled, filtered and the solid mass was warmed with a 5% NaOH solution to remove any unchanged methoxy compound. The filtrate was neutralised and the solid was collected and washed with cold water. On three crystallisations from ethanol, the compound melted at 269-70°. Mixed m.p. with the sample prepared as in (a) and (b) recorded no depression.

(d). Polyphosphoric acid was prepared by adding syrupy phosphoric acid (0.9 ml) to P₂O₅ (1.5 g.) and heating the resulting mixture on a steam bath until the solution was clear. β -*m*-Chloroanilino-*p*-methoxyanilido (0.003M, 1.05 g.) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid and then worked up essentially as described for cyclisation with H₂SO₄. The compound (50%, 0.4 g.) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 267-68°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample recorded no depression. The alkali-insoluble compound was found to be 6-methoxy-4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline. The IR spectra of the compound, prepared by different procedures, were all superimposable.

6-Methoxy-4-methyl-2-hydroxyquinoline.—*p*-Acetoacetaniside (0.5 g.) was added slowly to H₂SO₄ (conc., 1 ml), care being taken to maintain the temperature below 10°. After keeping overnight, the mixture was heated at 100° for 4 hr., cooled to the room temperature, and stirred with ice. The solid was collected, washed with water, and basified with ammonia. On crystallisation from a large volume of ethanol, the solid melted at 267-68° (lit.⁵ m.p. 268°).

7-Chloro-4-(4'-methoxyanilino)quinaldine.—(a). This was prepared from 4,7-dichloroquinaldine and *p*-anisidine hydrochloride in the usual way. The crude product on recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol melted at 188-89°, yield 86%.

(b). The cyclodehydration of β -*m*-chloroanilinoaceto-*p*-methoxyanilido was carried out with P₂O₅ in xylene, essentially according to the general method of Price and Boekelheide⁴. On recrystallisation from aqueous ethanol, the compound (22%) melted at 188-89°. Mixed m.p. with a sample prepared as in (a) recorded no depression. (Found: C, 68.51; H, 5.44; N, 9.46. C₁₇H₁₅ON₂Cl requires C, 68.34; H, 5.02; N, 9.38%.)